

Special
Collection

Physicochemical Characterization of Sparsely Tethered Bilayer Lipid Membranes: Structure of Submembrane Water and Nanomechanical Properties

Damian Dziubak and Sławomir Sek^{*[a]}Dedicated to Professor *Marcin Opałło* on the occasion of his 65th birthday.

Sparingly tethered bilayer lipid membrane (stBLM) is a popular model considered to mimic biological membranes. The advantage of this system is the molecular architecture that provides a water environment on both sides of the lipid membrane. In this work, we have coupled electrochemical measurements with surface enhanced infrared absorption spectroscopy and atomic force microscopy to evaluate the effect of the electric field on the physicochemical properties of stBLM composed of 1,2-dimyristoyl-*sn*-glycero-3-phosphocholine and cholesterol. More

specifically, we have focused on the structure of the submembrane water and nanomechanical properties of the membrane. Our experimental results revealed that stBLM composed of DMPC/Cholesterol offers good nanomechanical stability and low permeability within a relatively wide potential window. Importantly, it also covers biologically relevant range corresponding to transmembrane potentials occurring in natural cell membranes, which makes them suitable platform for bioinspired sensing devices.

1. Introduction

Simplified models of lipid bilayers with well-defined and controlled composition are often used as platforms for the studies of physicochemical properties of the lipid membranes and their interactions with relevant biomolecules.^[1,2] Among others, solid-supported lipid bilayers offer certain advantages related to broad range of surface-sensitive analytical techniques that can be used for membrane characterization. Moreover, the use of metallic substrates opens the wide range of possibilities to use such techniques in conjunction with electrochemical methods enabling investigation of the effects of external electric field on the behavior of lipid membranes. To some extent, this reflects the situation in biological systems where membranes are experiencing the electrochemical potential gradient. However, the direct immobilization of the lipid bilayer on the metal surface has significant limitations for the use of such systems as models of biological membranes due to the direct interaction of lipids with the metallic substrate, which may affect the structure of the bilayer. This differs from biological systems, where the membrane on both sides is in contact with the aqueous environment. To overcome these limitations specific model membranes have been proposed in which the lipid bilayer is separated from the electrode surface

either by strongly hydrophilic environment or a space filled by thin layer of water. Specific examples include polymer supported membranes and floating lipid bilayers.^[3,4] However, the stability of these architectures often does not meet the requirements for application in biosensing devices. To overcome these limitations, tethered bilayer lipid membranes (tBLMs) were developed to create biomimetic systems adapted for transmembrane protein characterization. In tBLMs, the lipid bilayer is separated from the surface of the substrate by flexible hydrophilic layer of spacers that anchor the proximal leaflet. In most cases, the hydrophilic spacer is composed of several oxyethylene units, while the anchoring group consist of thio-compound such as lipoic acid or cysteamine.^[5–7] Due to the good solubility in water, oxyethylene units were designed to behave as a water-rich hydrogel. However, the results based on IR measurements demonstrated that a substantial fraction of the ester groups in lipids forming tethered films is not hydrated.^[8] This indicates that the hydration in the spacer region is rather poor, and it results from a coiled conformation of oxyethylene units exposing the hydrophobic carbon segments to the surroundings when assembled into tBLMs. Similar conclusion comes from the neutron reflectivity measurements reported by Vockenroth and coworkers.^[9]

The model that is a compromise between the appropriate stability of the system and the need for strong hydration of the membrane from the substrate side is sparsely tethered bilayer lipid membrane (stBLM).^[10,11] Preparation of sparsely tethered bilayer lipid membranes (stBLM) involves pre-modification of metallic surface with two-component molecular film consisting of hydrophilic molecules, which play a role of a backfiller for co-adsorbed tethering molecules. The latter are usually lipids coupled with hydrophilic spacer and anchoring group. The lipid bilayer is deposited onto pre-modified metallic surface. The resulting lipid assembly is separated from

[a] D. Dziubak, Prof. S. Sek
Faculty of Chemistry, Biological & Chemical Research Centre
University of Warsaw
Zwirki i Wigury 101, 02-089 Warsaw, Poland
E-mail: slasek@chem.uw.edu.pl

 An invited contribution to the *Marcin Opałło Festschrift*.

 © 2021 The Authors. ChemElectroChem Published by Wiley-VCH GmbH. This is an open access article under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

the electrode by water cushion entrapped between backfiller and the membrane which is anchored to the surface by tethering molecules. Hence, the membrane is surrounded on both sides by an aqueous environment.^[12] Sparsely tethered bilayers were proved useful for characterization of transmembrane proteins since they provide enough space in the submembrane region to accommodate biomolecules which extend beyond the lipid bilayer.^[13] For this reason, such architecture of the lipid membrane is also used in biosensing devices.^[14,15] However, despite the wide use of stBLMs, their physicochemical characteristics still lacks some important information. Namely, it concerns the structure of water in the submembrane space and nanomechanical properties. The structure of the lipid headgroup region often depends on the nature of water in proximity of the membrane and this could be crucial in triggering the certain mechanisms that define the activity of numerous proteins.^[16] It could affect the secondary structure of a protein fragments located in the headgroup region, for example, the ends of transmembrane α -helices. Also, the nanomechanical properties of the membrane, which are strongly related to the presence of water molecules, can influence the activity of the transmembrane proteins.^[17] The way in which the membrane is deformed can affect the conformation of proteins. Therefore, when considering stBLM systems as a platform for protein incorporation, it is important to understand both the behavior of water molecules surrounding the membrane and its nanomechanical properties. In this work, we have combined electrochemical measurements with surface sensitive techniques including surface enhanced infrared absorption spectroscopy (EC-SEIRAS) and atomic force microscopy (EC-AFM) to address these issues and evaluate the potential-dependent behavior of stBLM composed of 1,2-dimyristoyl-*sn*-glycero-3-phosphocholine (DMPC) and cholesterol.

2. Results and Discussion

The model stBLM membrane used in this work was deposited on gold surface pre-modified with two-component monolayer composed of backfiller molecules of thioglucose and thiolipid tether (DPhSPL) where the molar ratio of the components was 9:1. The structure of the tethering thiolipid molecule is shown in Scheme 1.

After formation of two-component self-assembled monolayer the gold substrates were transferred to suspension of small unilamellar vesicles composed of 1,2-dimyristoyl-*sn*-glycero-3-phosphocholine (DMPC) and cholesterol at 7:3 molar ratio, and then left for the bilayer formation. The resulting sparsely tethered lipid bilayer membrane (stBLM) was further

Scheme 1. Chemical structure of tethering thiolipid DPhSPL.

subjected to physicochemical characterization. First, we have determined the potential of zero free charge (E_{pzfc}) for the electrode modified with stBLM composed of DMPC/Chol. For this purpose, we have used the immersion method.^[18] The working electrode with deposited membrane was placed above the electrolyte and polarized to the specified potential and then the electrode was lowered toward the electrolyte and the current flow was recorded upon contact. Under these conditions, the surface area of the electrode exposed to the solution changes at the fixed potential and the observed charging current is proportional to the charge per unit area of the electrode. Hence the currents recorded during the immersion reflect the charge flowing to the metal-solution interface to build the electrical double-layer at the given immersion potential.^[19]

The charge of the metal side can be obtained by integrating the immersion current at a given immersion potential. Figure 1 illustrates the plot of integrated charge as a function of the immersion potential. The fitted line intersects the zero charge point at the potential of 0.29 ± 0.03 V, which corresponds to the E_{pzfc} of the stBLM composed of DMPC/Cholesterol. The observed value is close to that observed for thioglucose-modified gold,^[19] which may indicate that interfacial charge distribution is dominated by the presence of the backfiller molecules. It is also more positive with respect to the E_{pzfc} observed for bare gold in 0.1 M NaF demonstrating that the presence of the backfiller inhibits adsorption of anions on electrode surface.^[19] Determination of the value of E_{pzfc} is useful for approximate determination of the transmembrane potential, which can be estimated as a difference between potential applied to the electrode (E) and the potential of zero free charge ($\varphi_{trans} = E - E_{pzfc}$).^[20] Knowing the value of the transmembrane potential, it is possible to compare the explored potential range to the values typical for biological membranes. Further, we have evaluated

Figure 1. Integrated charge as a function of immersion potential for stBLM immobilized on Au(111) electrode. The data was collected in an aqueous solution of 0.1 M NaF.

capacitive behavior of the lipid membranes based on AC voltammograms. This enables the assessment of the membrane stability in the presence of the external electric field. Potential-dependent changes in differential capacitance for stBLM composed of DMPC/Cholesterol are illustrated in Figure 2.

The region of the highest stability of the lipid membranes is characterized by the lowest values of the capacitance. The local minimum of the differential capacitance was observed within the range of $0.12 \text{ V} \div 0.25 \text{ V}$, with the lowest value of $5.1 \mu\text{F cm}^{-2}$, which is comparable to the values reported for tethered bilayer lipid membranes with ionic reservoirs.^[21,22] The minimum is located slightly more negative with respect to the potential of zero free charge determined for stBLM. It corresponds to the transmembrane potentials of $-0.04 \div -0.17 \text{ V}$, hence, it covers the range typically observed for natural membranes. More negative polarization of the electrode causes slight increase of the capacitance but at the potentials more negative than -0.6 V the capacitance grows more rapidly and finally pseudocapacitive peak is observed. The latter reflects the detachment of the lipid film from the electrode surface. At the potential close to -1.2 V , the capacitance is around $20 \mu\text{F cm}^{-2}$. This value correlates with capacitance of film-free Au(111) electrode, which indicates complete detachment of lipid bilayer as well as desorption of thiolated molecules, i.e. thioglucose and DPhSPL.

More detailed information regarding the stability and homogeneity of the membrane can be gathered using electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS). This method enables detection of defects in lipid membrane and assessment of its permeability.^[23,24] Figure 3(A) shows the EIS spectra recorded for stBLM between 0.2 V and -0.4 V . The impedance does not vary significantly within this potential region and the responses are linear within most of the frequency range, which is considered

Figure 2. Differential capacitance vs. potential curves measured for DMPC/Cholesterol stBLM (solid line) and for bare Au(111) electrode in 0.1 M NaF (dotted line).

Figure 3. (A) Exemplary EIS spectra (Bode plot) obtained for Au(111) electrode modified with DMPC/Cholesterol stBLM. The data was collected in an aqueous solution of 0.1 M NaF at the potentials ranging from 0.2 V to -0.4 V . Solid lines represent the fits of the equivalent circuit shown as inset. (B) Membrane resistance and CPE_m as a function of the potential applied to working electrode. Error bars represent the standard deviation between independent experiments.

as characteristic for capacitive systems.^[25] This is confirmed by the phase angle vs. frequency plots, which display a plateau in the frequency range of $1\text{--}100 \text{ Hz}$, with the phase angle values exceeding 80° . Such behavior indicates that the total impedance is primarily controlled by capacitance of the system and the membranes have low density of defects. More quantitative information related to the permeability of the membranes can be obtained based on analysis of membrane resistance. This parameter can be extracted from EIS data upon equivalent circuit fitting. The scheme of the equivalent circuit representing stBLM immobilized on the electrode is shown as inset in Figure 3(A) and it consists of electrolyte solution resistance (R_{sol}), membrane resistance (R_m), constant phase element of bilayer membrane (CPE_m) and constant phase element of submem-

brane space region (CPE_{sp}). The changes of membrane resistance in the potential region between 0.2 V and -0.4 V are shown in Figure 3(B). The membrane resistance ranges from $0.9 \text{ M}\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ to $1.4 \text{ M}\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ which manifests good insulating properties and relatively low permeability for ions and water molecules, which means that the density of defects is low. Similar range of the values of membrane resistance was also observed for other stBLMs systems which show good insulating properties.^[7] The same figure shows the dependence of CPE_m on the potential applied to the electrode. This parameter can be considered as approximate measure of the membrane capacitance since the values of α were found to be >0.94 . Within the potential range of $0.2 \div -0.1$ V, the CPE_m is below $5.0 \mu\text{F cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{\alpha-1}$. At more negative potentials, CPE_m begins to rise gradually up to $\sim 9.0 \mu\text{F cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{\alpha-1}$. These changes are consistent with the results obtained from ACV, where similar potential dependence was observed for differential capacitance. Similar range of the capacitances was also reported for floating bilayer lipid membranes with good insulating properties.^[26]

Integrity of the membrane and its morphology was verified using atomic force microscopy. Figure 4(A) illustrates the image of stBLM recorded at the potential of 0.2 V. It proves that DMPC/Cholesterol forms continuous film without visible defect sites. The morphology of the bilayer displays faint corrugation, which locally has quasi-regular pattern indicating high ordering of lipids within the assembly. The surface roughness determined for DMPC/Cholesterol bilayer was 0.15 ± 0.03 nm. Interestingly, this structure is preserved within the entire potential window ranging from 0.2 V to -0.4 V. Noticeable changes occur

Figure 4. AFM images illustrating the morphology of DMPC/Cholesterol stBLM immobilized on Au(111) electrode at the potential of 0.2 V (A) and -0.5 V (B). Panel (C) shown the variation of the Young's modulus determined for DMPC/Cholesterol stBLM as a function of the potential applied to Au(111) electrode.

at the potential of -0.5 V. The relevant AFM image is shown in Figure 4(B). In this case, the morphology of the bilayer becomes irregular, and the surface roughness is noticeably increased up to 0.60 ± 0.09 nm, which may reflect the membrane swelling. Moreover, numerous aggregates as well as cavities can be distinguished on AFM image indicating that the membrane integrity is disturbed. To explore the membrane properties in more details, we have also performed AFM-based nanomechanical analysis of the DMPC/Cholesterol bilayer, which enable determination of Young's modulus. This parameter describes the elastic properties of the surface film. The changes of Young's modulus as a function of the potential applied to the electrode are demonstrated in Figure 4(C). Young's modulus remains virtually constant between 0.2 V and -0.3 V and its value is only slightly decreased at the potential of -0.4 V. The average value of the Young's modulus within this region is close to 7.0 MPa. Interestingly, this value is significantly lower compared to moduli of elasticity reported for other architectures of solid supported lipid membranes. For example, the Young's moduli found for lipid bilayers immobilized on mica vary from 18 MPa to 40 MPa depending on physical state of the membrane.^[27,28] Similar range of values was also reported for floating bilayer lipid membranes (fBLM).^[29] The latter possess water cushion between lipid membrane and the electrode modified with hydrophilic monolayer (e.g. thioglucose). Therefore, its architecture is to some extent similar to stBLM with the exception that fBLMs are lacking the poly(oxyethylene) spacers anchoring the membrane to the electrode surface. However, this subtle difference could significantly affect their submembrane region. Namely, the amount and the structure of submembrane water may be substantially altered and consequently, it may affect nanomechanical properties of the membrane. As we demonstrated recently, the growth of water cushion separating the lipid membrane from the electrode surface leads to gradual decrease of the Young's modulus.^[29] Therefore, relatively low value of the modulus determined for stBLM may indicate that submembrane water reservoir is thicker compared with fBLMs as well as other lipid membranes, which are deposited directly on the supporting surface. Small changes in Young's modulus observed between 0.2 V and -0.4 V demonstrate that the bilayer does not undergo significant structural changes within the specified potential range. Moreover, it can also be concluded that the amount of water in the submembrane region does not vary significantly. However, when the potential is stepped to -0.5 V, the value of the Young's modulus noticeably drops, and the gradual reduction of the modulus value is maintained during further negative polarization of the electrode. This proves that the membrane becomes less rigid. Such behavior may reflect increased disorder and membrane swelling due to increased flux of water and ions when the polarization of the electrode approaches desorption potential.

To explore the nature of the submembrane region, we have performed surface enhanced infrared absorption spectroscopy (SEIRAS) measurements. In this technique, the electromagnetic field of the incident beam excites the local plasmon and induces an oscillating dipole in the gold nanoparticles depos-

ited on the planar surface of the silicon prism.^[30] The dipole produces an electric field in the vicinity of the nanoparticle which can excite the molecules adsorbed on gold surface. The local electric field in the vicinity of the gold particles decays sharply within the distance of several nanometers from the surface. This distance is comparable to the thickness of the membrane deposited on the electrode surface. Hence, the absorption by the bulk of solution is small. Moreover, it can be perfectly canceled by collecting potential difference spectra. Therefore, this technique is considered as powerful tool for probing electrode-electrolyte interface.^[31–33] Consequently, it can also bring important information on the structure of submembrane water in stBLM systems.

Potential-dependent differential SEIRA spectra collected for the membrane composed of DMPC/Cholesterol are presented in Figure 5(A). The reference potential was 0.3 V. Initially, the potential step to 0.2 V affects the spectra little indicating that the amount and the structure of water in submembrane reservoir remains practically unchanged. However, further potential steps towards -0.4 V result in appearance of complex $\nu(\text{O-H})$ band with both positive and negative components.

Figure 5. Potential-dependent differential SEIRA spectra recorded for DMPC/Cholesterol stBLM deposited on gold surface within the $\nu(\text{O-H})$ region (A) and $\nu(\text{C-H})$ region (B). The reference spectra were collected at the potential of 0.3 V. The measurements were performed in 0.1 M NaF.

More specifically, positive components emerge in the region between 3200 cm^{-1} and 3550 cm^{-1} , while negative bands appear for higher frequencies with local minima at $\sim 3620\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 3769\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The positive $\nu(\text{O-H})$ band display global maximum located at $\sim 3400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ with distinct shoulder at $\sim 3280\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating that highly ordered hydrogen-bonded “liquid-like” water and “ice-like” water is accumulated at the interface when the electrode surface becomes more negatively charged. However, the emergence of negative bands at $\sim 3620\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 3769\text{ cm}^{-1}$ implies that disordered monomeric water is simultaneously removed from submembrane region. Hence, SEIRAS results suggest that negative polarization of the electrode surface causes efflux of disordered monomeric water, which is accompanied by influx of ordered hydrogen-bonded water. On the other hand, the AFM data demonstrated that the membrane structure and its nanomechanical properties remain unchanged between 0.2 V and -0.4 V. At the same time, the EIS data showed that the permeability of the membrane is rather low within the specified potential region, which may indicate that the transmembrane flux of water and ions is hindered. Therefore, an alternative scenario can be considered in this case, which involves ordering of water molecules in submembrane reservoir. Namely, the water molecules reorganize in the submembrane region from disordered monomeric state to hydrogen-bonded state when the charge of the electrode becomes more negative. At the potentials lower than -0.4 V further development of the positive and negative component of the $\nu(\text{O-H})$ band is observed, and such trend is preserved to the potential of -0.7 V. However, within this region, the absolute intensities of the peaks seem to grow more rapidly compared with the range of $0.2 \div -0.4$ V, which may indicate that the source of the changes in the intensity of the bands is different in this region. Such an assumption seems reasonable when considering AFM results, which demonstrated that the membrane undergoes structural transition at the potential of -0.5 V and the integrity of the membrane is disturbed. The latter can certainly facilitate flux of water through the membrane. Also, AC voltammetry data indicates that the potential region between -0.5 V and -0.7 V corresponds to the onset of the desorption process. It means that the surface film is gradually replaced with water giving rise to stronger absorption in $\nu(\text{O-H})$. Additional information regarding the potential-induced changes in lipid membrane can be gathered based on analysis of $\nu(\text{C-H})$ stretching region. In SEIRAS, the molecular vibrations with the component of the transition dipole moment normal to the local surface can be excited and enhanced. Hence, the intensity of the absorption depends on both, the amount of the deposited material and the orientation of the adsorbed molecules with respect to the surface normal.^[34] As shown in Figure 5(B), polarization of the electrode between 0.2 V and -0.4 V does not affect the spectra and the $\nu(\text{C-H})$ bands are absent. Therefore, we can conclude that the amount as well as the orientation of lipid molecules does not change within this potential window. Similar behavior was reported by Matyszewska and coworkers for fBLMs where the DMPC bilayer was separated from the electrode surface by water cushion.^[35] These

authors have shown that polarization of the electrode causes rather limited changes in orientation of the acyl chains. The tilt angle with respect to the surface normal varied from $\sim 18^\circ$ for positive potentials to $\sim 14^\circ$ for negative potentials and the observed differences were within experimental uncertainties. For stBLM studied in this work, polarization of the electrode to the potential of -0.5 V results in the occurrence of the negative $\nu(\text{C-H})$ bands and their intensity increases with further potential steps towards more negative values. This can be interpreted either in terms of the decreased tilt angle of lipids chain with respect to the surface normal (transition dipole moment of C-H bond becomes more parallel to the surface) or decreased amount of hydrocarbon chains/lipids close to the electrode surface.^[33] Both effects may be ascribed to the onset of the membrane desorption, which is in line with the results obtained from AC voltammetry and AFM measurements.

3. Conclusions

Our results indicate that stBLM composed of DMPC/Cholesterol (7:3 molar ratio) display good stability and low permeability at the potentials from 0.2 V to -0.4 V. The membrane resistance is in the range of $M\Omega$, which prove low permeability of the system for water and ions. The integrity of the lipid film was confirmed by AFM imaging. Nanomechanical measurements proved that elastic properties of the bilayer do not vary within the specified potential region suggesting that membrane perforation or swelling is limited. Interestingly, the Young's modulus determined for stBLM is noticeably lower compared with other lipid membrane architectures, e.g. fBLMs. It can be interpreted in terms of either thicker or differently structured water cushion separating the bilayer from the electrode surface. Although the morphology of the membrane and its permeability was preserved between 0.2 V and -0.4 V, the analysis of the SEIRA spectra revealed that the content of water in the submembrane space and its ordering varies. Namely, the gradual increase of ordered hydrogen-bonded water content was observed during the negative polarization, while the disordered monomeric water was simultaneously removed from the submembrane reservoir. Considering the stability of the bilayer in the considered potential range, it can be concluded that the water molecules are reorganized in the submembrane region when the charge of the electrode becomes more negative. However, polarization of the electrode to potentials more negative than -0.4 V causes disruption of the membrane structure, which significantly increases flux of water and ions as can be concluded from SEIRA spectra. It also deteriorates the elastic properties of the membrane and substantial drop in Young's modulus is observed. To sum up, our results demonstrate that stBLM composed of DMPC/Cholesterol offers good stability and low permeability within relatively wide potential window. Importantly, it also covers biologically relevant range corresponding to transmembrane potentials occurring in natural cell membranes. This makes this system useful for both, fundamental studies of transmembrane proteins/channels and applications in biosensing devices.

Experimental Section

Chemicals

Succinic anhydride, 4-(dimethylamino)pyridine (DMAP), N-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)-N'-ethylcarbodiimide hydrochloride (EDC), N-hydroxysuccinimide (NHS), trifluoroacetic acid, N-Boc-4,7,10-trioxa-1,13-tridecanediamine, 1,2-di-O-phytanyl-sn-glycerol, lipoic acid, 1,2-dimyristoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphocholine (DMPC), cholesterol (Chol), chloroform, anhydrous methylene chloride, 1-thio- β -D-glucose, and sodium fluoride were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Methanol, triethylamine, hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2), anhydrous magnesium sulfate, citric acid and sodium bicarbonate and sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4) were purchased from POCh Gliwice. Water solutions were prepared with ultrapure water passed through Milli-Q system (final resistivity $18.2 M\Omega \times \text{cm}$). All electrochemical and spectroelectrochemical measurements were performed in 0.1 M NaF aqueous solution.

Synthesis of Lipid Tether

First step of the synthesis involved formation of 1,2-di-O-phytanyl-sn-glycero-3-succinate. 50 mg of 1,2-di-O-phytanyl-sn-glycerol was dissolved in 25 mL of anhydrous methylene chloride and then 9.4 mg of DMAP and 15.3 mg of succinic anhydride was added. The mixture was stirred for 24 h at room temperature under the atmosphere of argon. After that, the mixture containing 1,2-di-O-phytanyl-sn-glycero-3-succinate was washed with an aqueous solution of 1 M HCl and the organic phase was separated and dried over anhydrous MgSO_4 for 12 h. Then the solution was filtered. The second step involved activation of the terminal carboxylic group in 1,2-di-O-phytanyl-sn-glycero-3-succinate and its coupling with N-Boc-4,7,10-trioxa-1,13-tridecanediamine. To achieve this, 17.2 mg of EDC and 10.2 mg of NHS was added to the solution obtained in the first step, and the mixture was stirred for 30 minutes to activate the carboxylic groups. Then, 10 mL of the methylene chloride solution containing 24 mg of N-Boc-4,7,10-trioxa-1,13-tridecanediamine and $\sim 14 \mu\text{L}$ of triethylamine was added, and the resulting mixture was stirred 24 h at room temperature. Subsequently, the reaction mixture was washed with 50 mL of saturated aqueous solution of NaHCO_3 , 50 mL of citric acid (10% aq.), again 50 mL of saturated aqueous solution of NaHCO_3 and 50 mL of water. The organic phase containing 1,2-di-O-phytanyl-sn-glycero-3-succinate coupled by amide bond with N-Boc-4,7,10-trioxa-1,13-tridecanediamine was dried over anhydrous MgSO_4 and then it was filtered. In the next step, Boc protecting group was removed by addition of 2 mL of trifluoroacetic acid and stirring for ~ 2.5 h. The last step involved the coupling of lipoic acid to deprotected terminal amine group of the modified lipid. First the lipoic acid was activated and for that purpose, 18 mg of lipoic acid, 17 mg of EDC and 10 mg of NHS was dissolved in 20 mL of methylene chloride and the solution was stirred for 30 minutes. In parallel, 2 mL of triethylamine was added directly to the lipid solution from previous step. Next, both solutions were mixed and the coupling reaction was carried out for 24 h with continuous stirring. The resulting reaction mixture was washed with 50 mL of saturated aqueous solution of NaHCO_3 , 50 mL of citric acid (10% aq.), again 50 mL of saturated aqueous solution of NaHCO_3 and 50 mL of water and then dried over anhydrous MgSO_4 for ~ 6 h. Then the solution was filtered, and the solvent was evaporated using rotary evaporator. The product was thick yellowish oil. The identity of the product was confirmed by mass spectrometry ESI-MS $[M + \text{Na}^+] = 1165.88$ ($M_{\text{calc.}} = 1142.89$ g/mol).

Lipid Vesicles Preparation

Stock solutions of DMPC/Chol (7:3 molar ratio) were prepared in chloroform and the total lipid concentration was 1 mg/mL. A portion of ~0.25 mL of stock solution was placed in Eppendorf tube and the solvent was evaporated by vortexing under Ar stream. Subsequently, the tubes with a dry lipid cake were transferred to a vacuum desiccator to remove the residues of the solvent. The samples were desiccated for 1.5–2 hours followed by the addition of 0.1 M NaF aqueous solution. Then, the samples were bath sonicated at 37 °C for 1 hour to obtain a transparent suspension of small unilamellar vesicles (SUVs).

Electrodes Preparation

Before each measurement, Au(111) electrodes were cleaned in piranha solution (a mixture of H₂SO₄ and H₂O₂, volume ratio 3:1), washed by ultrapure water, and flame-annealed. Gold surface was pre-modified with two-component monolayer composed of β-thioglucose/DPhSPL (9:1 molar ratio). The self-assembly was carried out from methanolic solutions and the immersion time was ~6 h. After that, the electrodes were thoroughly rinsed with methanol and water. Next, the electrodes were transferred to SUVs suspension and left overnight for bilayer formation.

Electrochemistry

Alternative current voltammetry (ACV) and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurements were carried out using CHI 750B potentiostat (CH Instruments, Inc., Austin, TX) with a three-electrode configuration. The platinum foil was used as the counter electrode and Ag|AgCl|0.1 M KCl aq. was used as a reference electrode. Single crystal Au(111) electrodes were used as working electrodes. The measurements were performed in hanging meniscus configuration. ACV experiments were performed with 5 mVs⁻¹ scan rate, an amplitude of 10 mV and a frequency of 20 Hz. The capacitance were calculated from the in-phase and out-of-phase components of the current assuming a simple RC circuit. The EIS measurements were performed within the frequency range of 10⁻¹–10⁴ Hz at the potentials between 0.2 and -0.4 V with the step of -0.1 V. The amplitude was set at 0.01 V. The obtained impedance spectra was fitted to $R_{sol}-CPE_m(R_m CPE_{sp})$ equivalent circuit, where R_{sol} is a resistance of the solvent, R_m is a resistance of the membrane, CPE_m is a constant phase element for the membrane and the CPE_{sp} is a constant phase element corresponding to the submembrane region between the bilayer and Au(111) surface. Potential of zero free charge (E_{pzc}) was determined by immersion method. All potentials are reported with reference to Ag|AgCl|0.1 M KCl aq. electrode.

Atomic Force Microscopy

The imaging of lipid membranes and nanomechanical measurements were performed using Dimension Icon (Bruker, Santa Barbara, CA) instrument. The images were collected in an aqueous 0.1 M NaF under electrochemical conditions with Pt wire serving as a counter electrode and miniaturized Ag|AgCl|0.1 M KCl aq. as a reference electrode. The imaging and nanomechanical mapping were carried out within the potential range of 0.2 ÷ -0.7 V. ScanAsyst Fluid probes (Bruker, Santa Barbara, CA) with nominal spring constant of 0.7 N/m were used in all experiments. The probes were calibrated using the thermal tune method. For nanomechanical measurements, we have used Peak Force QNM mode, where the AFM probe is modulated at default amplitude with the frequency of 2 kHz and the instrument collects force-

distance curves at every pixel of the scanned area. Derjaguin, Muller, Toporov (DMT) model of contact mechanics was used for the determination of Young's modulus of the samples.

Surface-Enhanced Infrared Absorption Spectroscopy

The Surface-Enhanced Infrared Absorption Spectroscopy (SEIRAS) spectra were collected by Nicolet iS50 FTIR spectrometer (Thermo Scientific) equipped with nitrogen cooled highly sensitive MCT-A detector and a custom-made single-reflection accessory. The resolution of the spectra was 4 cm⁻¹ and the incident angle was 60°. The spectra were collected in the range of the potentials between 0.3 V and -0.7 V with -0.1 V step and they are presented in absorbance units calculated according to formula $A = \log(I_0/I)$, where A is absorbance, I_0 and I represent the intensities of IR radiation observed for the reference potential (0.3 V) and the measured potential, respectively. The potential was controlled by CHI 750B potentiostat (CH Instruments, Inc., Austin, TX). The reference electrode was Ag|AgCl|0.1 M KCl aq. and the counter electrode was platinum foil. The working electrode was the thin gold film deposited onto the reflectance plane of Si hemispherical prism. Deposition of gold was performed by placing an aqueous plating solution onto the hydrogen-terminated Si surface. Said plating solution was prepared by mixing 100 μL of 0.03 M NaAuCl₄·2H₂O, 2 mL of 0.15 M Na₂SO₃ + 0.05 M Na₂S₂O₃·5H₂O + 0.05 M NH₄Cl, and 1 mL of 2% HF. After approximately 90 s of plating, the prism was rinsed with ultrapure water to terminate the deposition. The resulting gold film was further modified with stBLM according to the same protocol as described earlier.

Acknowledgements

This research was funded by Polish National Science Centre, Project No. 2016/21/B/ST4/02122. The study was carried out at the Biological and Chemical Research Centre, University of Warsaw, established within the project co-financed by European Union from the European Regional Development Fund under the Operational Program Innovative Economy, 2007–2013.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Keywords: electrochemistry · sparsely tethered bilayers lipid membranes · surface enhanced infrared absorption spectroscopy · atomic force microscopy · biosensing

- [1] D. Grieshaber, R. MacKenzie, J. Vörös, E. Reimhult, *Sensors* **2008**, *8*, 1400–1458.
- [2] Z. Su, J. J. Leitch, J. Lipkowski, *Curr. Opin. Electrochem.* **2018**, *12*, 60–72.
- [3] J. Y. Wong, J. Majewski, M. Seitz, C. K. Park, J. N. Israelachvili, G. S. Smith, *Biophys. J.* **1999**, *77*, 1445–1457.
- [4] A. H. Kycia, J. Wang, A. R. Merrill, J. Lipkowski, *Langmuir* **2011**, *27*, 10867–10877.
- [5] A. Junghans, I. Köper, *Langmuir* **2010**, *26*, 11035–11040.
- [6] S. M. Schiller, R. Naumann, K. Lovejoy, H. Kunz, W. Knoll, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2003**, *42*, 208–211; *Angew. Chem.* **2003**, *115*, 219–222.
- [7] J. Andersson, J. J. Knobloch, M. V. Perkins, S. A. Holt, I. Köper, *Langmuir* **2017**, *33*, 4444–4451.

- [8] J. Leitch, J. Kunze, J. D. Goddard, A. L. Schwan, R. J. Faragher, R. Naumann, W. Knoll, J. R. Dutcher, J. Lipkowski, *Langmuir* **2009**, *25*, 10354–10363.
- [9] I. K. Vockenroth, C. Rossi, M. R. Shah, I. Köper, *Biointerphases* **2009**, *4*, 19–26.
- [10] B. Raguse, V. Braach-Maksytytis, B. A. Cornell, L. G. King, P. D. J. Osman, R. J. Pace, L. Wieczorek, *Langmuir* **1998**, *14*, 648–659.
- [11] F. Heinrich, T. Ng, D. J. Vanderah, P. Shekhar, M. Mihailescu, H. Nanda, M. Lösche, *Langmuir* **2009**, *25*, 4219–4229.
- [12] D. J. McGillivray, G. Valincius, D. J. Vanderah, W. Febo-Ayala, J. T. Woodward, F. Heinrich, J. J. Kasianowicz, M. Lösche, *Biointerphases* **2007**, *2*, 21–33.
- [13] J. Andersson, I. Köper, W. Knoll, *Front. Mater.* **2018**, *5*, 55.
- [14] B. A. Cornell, V. L. Braach-Maksytytis, L. G. King, P. D. Osman, B. Raguse, L. Wieczorek, R. J. Pace, *Nature* **1997**, *387*, 580–583.
- [15] W. Zhou, P. J. Burke, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2017**, *9*, 14618–14632.
- [16] A. G. Lee, *Biochim. Biophys. Acta* **2004**, *1666*, 62–87.
- [17] J. J. Kinnun, K. J. Mallikarjunaiah, H. I. Petrache, M. F. Brown, *Biochim. Biophys. Acta Biomembr.* **2015**, *1848*, 246–259.
- [18] U. W. Hamm, D. Kramer, R. S. Zhai, D. M. Kolb, *J. Electroanal. Chem.* **1996**, *414*, 85–89.
- [19] Z. Su, J. Leitch, J. Lipkowski, *Zeitschrift für Phys. Chemie* **2012**, *226*, 995.
- [20] F. Abbasi, J. Alvarez-Malmagro, Z. Su, J. J. Leitch, J. Lipkowski, *Langmuir* **2018**, *34*, 13754–13765.
- [21] G. Krishna, J. Schulte, B. A. Cornell, R. Pace, L. Wieczorek, P. D. Osman, *Langmuir* **2001**, *17*, 4858–4866.
- [22] H. Basit, A. Van der Heyden, C. Gondran, B. Nysten, P. Dumy, P. Labbé, *Langmuir* **2011**, *27*, 14317–14328.
- [23] G. Valincius, T. Meškauskas, F. Ivanauskas, *Langmuir* **2012**, *28*, 977–990.
- [24] G. Valincius, M. Mickevicius, Tethered Phospholipid Bilayer Membranes. An Interpretation of the Electrochemical Impedance Response, Elsevier Inc., **2015**.
- [25] G. Valincius, M. Mickevicius, T. Penkauskas, M. Jankunec, *Electrochim. Acta* **2016**, *222*, 904–913.
- [26] D. Dziubak, K. Strzelak, S. Sek, *Membranes* **2021**, *11*, 11.
- [27] L. Picas, F. Rico, S. Scheuring, *Biophys. J.* **2012**, *102*, L01–L03.
- [28] D. Konarzewska, J. Juhaniwicz, A. Güzeloğlu, S. Sęk, *Biochim. Biophys. Acta Biomembr.* **2017**, *1859*, 475–483.
- [29] J. Juhaniwicz-Dębińska, D. Konarzewska, S. Sęk, *Langmuir* **2019**, *35*, 9422–9429.
- [30] M. Osawa, in *Diffraction Spectroscopy Methods Electrochem.* **2008**, pp. 269–314.
- [31] K. Ataka, T. Yotsuyanagi, M. Osawa, *J. Phys. Chem.* **1996**, *100*, 10664–10672.
- [32] M. Grossutti, J. J. Leitch, R. Seenath, M. Karaskiewicz, J. Lipkowski, *Langmuir* **2015**, *31*, 4411–4418.
- [33] T. Uchida, M. Osawa, J. Lipkowski, *J. Electroanal. Chem.* **2014**, *716*, 112–119.
- [34] M. Osawa, K.-I. Ataka, M. Ikeda, H. Uchihara, R. Nanba, *Anal. Sci.* **1991**, *7*, 503–506.
- [35] D. Matyszewska, R. Bilewicz, Z. Su, F. Abbasi, J. J. Leitch, J. Lipkowski, *Langmuir* **2016**, *32*, 1791–1798.

Manuscript received: May 28, 2021

Revised manuscript received: June 22, 2021